

Rhenium. Part IV*. Acid Association of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ and Formation of Dipyridine Compounds

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The acid association constant for the protonation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ to $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4]^{+2}$ has been determined potentiometrically by Bjerrum's method and $\log k$ found to be 1.7 at 27°. There was no indication of the formation of the diprotonated species. By the action of very dilute HCl on $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ two products of substantially the same composition $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ have been isolated. The violet form slowly changes to the green form on standing. The IR spectra of the violet form gave both O-H and $\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretching frequencies, while the green form gave $\text{Re} = \text{O}$, but no O-H band. Boiling of either of these two products or of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with strong HCl gave a green precipitate of nonelectrolytic $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes have been reported.

On the addition of a strong acid to a solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ an intense pink colour is developed. From a solution containing hydrochloric acid Lebedinskii and Ivanov-Emin¹ have isolated salts of the ion $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4]^{+2}$. From a solution containing the analogous ethylene diamine compound $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$ and different concentrations of hydrochloric acid the same authors² have isolated salts of the ions $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{en}_2]^{+2}$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{en}_2]^{+3}$. In the presence of acid the tetrapyridine compound is also expected to undergo similar protonation :

The successive acid association constants have been determined potentiometrically by Bjerrum's method by applying Kelvin-Wilson titration technique. The formation function was calculated by using the equation

$$\bar{n} = \frac{A - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]}{C}$$

where C is the initial concentration of the salt $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ taken and A is the concentration of hydrochloric acid added to it at any stage of titration. The pH values recorded in titration were converted to free hydrogen ion concentrations $[\text{H}^+]$, by the conventional pH-pc calibration curve obtained by plotting the negative logarithms of stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentrations of solutions of standard hydrochloric acid against the observed pH values of the same solutions under similar experimental conditions. The first acid association cons-

* Preliminary notes on the work were published in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 81, and 1967, **44**, 654.

1. V. V. Lebedinskii and B. N. Ivanov-Emin, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1959, **4**, 794.
2. Idem, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1943, **13**, 253.

tant was calculated from the \bar{n} values from six points covering the middle portion of the titration upto the addition of approximately one equivalent of acid by using the equation

$$k_1 = \frac{\bar{n}}{[\text{H}^+](1-\bar{n})}$$

Since the value of \bar{n} did not exceed 0.4, the value of k_2 could not be determined. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Titration of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4] \text{Cl}$ (50 ml; $1.111 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) with HCl (0.472 M) at 27°

Vol. of acid added ml	pH observed	Molar concentration of rhenium complex $C \times 10^2$	Molar concentration of acid added $A \times 10^2$	pc	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^2$ calculated from pc	\bar{n}	k_1^*
0	5.53	1.111	—	—	—	—	
0.10	4.51	1.109	0.094	—	0.003	0.082	
0.20	3.33	1.107	0.188	3.24	0.057	0.118	
0.30	2.95	1.104	0.281	2.85	0.141	0.127	
0.40	2.74	1.103	0.375	2.64	0.229	0.133	67
0.50	2.60	1.100	0.467	2.50	0.316	0.137	63
0.60	2.50	1.097	0.560	2.39	0.407	0.139	51
0.70	2.42	1.096	0.652	2.31	0.490	1.148	46
0.80	2.34	1.093	0.743	2.24	0.575	0.154	40
0.90	2.29	1.091	0.834	2.18	0.661	0.158	37
1.00	2.24	1.089	0.925	2.13	0.741	0.169	
1.20	2.15	1.085	1.106	2.04	0.912	0.179	
1.50	2.04	1.078	1.375	1.93	1.175	0.185	
2.00	1.91	1.069	1.815	1.80	1.535	0.215	
2.50	1.81	1.058	2.247	1.70	1.995	0.238	
3.00	1.73	1.048	2.671	1.62	2.399	0.259	
3.50	1.66	1.039	3.087	1.55	2.818	0.259	
4.00	1.61	1.029	3.496	1.50	3.162	0.325	
5.00	1.52	1.010	4.290	1.41	3.890	0.396	

* Values of H^+ taken directly from pH. Average value of $k_1 = 51$. $\log k_1 = 1.7$.

Two products of substantially the same composition $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ have been isolated by the action of very dilute hydrochloric acid in cold on $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. The violet form on standing slowly turns dirty green and finally green without any change in composition.

It appears that the two forms are cis-trans isomers, or the violet form might polymerise to give the green one. Boiling of either of the green or the violet complex or $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with 6*N* or concentrated HCl gave a green precipitate of nonelectrolytic $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$. The magnetic susceptibility and the IR spectrum of these substances have been studied (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Magnetic susceptibility and IR spectral bands of the complexes

Compound	Temp °K	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi'_M \times 10^6$	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν , cm^{-1}
Violet $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$	306	-242	-45	—	3330 s, 1625 s, 1370 m, 1218 m, 1150 w, 1064 m, 1048 m, 978 s, 755 s, 765 m, 710 w, 682 w, 644 w.
Green $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$	306	0	197	0.70	1615 s, 1380 w, 1218 m, 1165 w, 1070 m, 1053 m, 980 m, 755 vs, 765 s, 697 w, 688 w, 676 w, 644 w.
$\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$	303	-120	89	0.49	1625 s, 1490 m, 1450 vs, 1350 w, 1240 w, 1210 s, 1065 vs, 1045 w, 1018 m, 970 vs, 940 m, 760 vs, 680 vs.

EXPERIMENTAL

$[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was prepared by the method described in a previous communication³. The analysis of Re, Cl, C, H and N, the determination of the oxidation state of Re, the determination of magnetic susceptibility and the recording of IR spectra were made by procedures published earlier^{3,5}.

pH measurements: A Cambridge Bench type pH meter was used for pH measurements. The instrument was calibrated with a buffer solution of pH 3.03 and the calibration was checked before and after the pH measurements with another buffer solution of pH 9/6. A Cambridge glass electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode was used for pH measurements.

A standard solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of the recrystallised anhydrous sample in a known volume of water. Requisite volume of 1.0 *M*

3. M. C. Chakravorti, Part I of this series *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, No. 9.

4. N. S. Gill, R. H. Nuttall, D. E. Scaife and D. W. A. Sharp, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.

5. M. C. Chakravorti, Part III of this series *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, No. 9.

potassium chloride was added to it to make the solution 0.5 *M* with respect to KCl (ionic strength 0.5). Hydrochloric acid solution which was also made 0.5 *M* with respect to KCl was standardised against standard alkali solution.

For plotting the *pH*-*pc* calibration curve 50.0 ml of 0.5 *M* KCl solution was "blank titrated" with the same hydrochloric acid solution and the *pH* values were recorded at each stage of addition of hydrochloric acid.

Conductivity measurements were made using a Philips conductivity measuring bridge (No. PR 9500/90) and using a dip type cell. A saturated aqueous solution of $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$ was made by vigorously shaking about 0.2 g of the substance with a large volume of conductivity water at room temperature (30°). This was then filtered and with a portion of the filtrate the conductance was measured immediately. With 500 ml of the filtrate rhenium was estimated electrogravimetrically after decomposing the compound in it by boiling with sodium peroxide and subsequent separation of rhenium as heptasulphide and conversion to perrhenate by alkali and hydrogen peroxide. The measured specific conductance of the solution was corrected for the specific conductance of the water used.

Preparation of the complexes: Violet and green forms of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$.—2.0 g of finely powdered $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved with stirring in about 100 ml of 0.4 *N* HCl. The deep red solution was allowed to stand with occasional stirring. A dirty green precipitate appeared initially which was gradually contaminated with a violet substance. After 24 hours the precipitate was separated by filtration, washed repeatedly with 0.4 *N* HCl and then with ethanol. The dark green residue was extracted with acetone to give a deep pink solution leaving behind a green substance. This green residue was washed thoroughly with acetone and dried over H_2SO_4 . The deep pink acetone extract was evaporated in air to give a violet substance which was then dried over H_2SO_4 . The yield of the green substance was about 1.0 g and that of the violet one about 100 mg.

Anal. of the green compound : Re, 40.9; Cl, 16.0; N, 6.4%.

Anal. of the violet compound : Re, 41.5; Cl, 15.2; N, 6.1%.

Calcd. for $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$: Re, 41.6; Cl, 15.8; N, 6.2%.

$\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$.—30 ml of conc. HCl was added to 1.0 g of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the mixture stirred. The intensely pink coloured solution containing a little suspension was refluxed for 2 hours during which time the pink colour disappeared with the separation of a green substance. After cooling, it was filtered under suction and washed successively with 1*N* HCl, water, ethanol and finally with acetone. It was then dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The yield was about 0.6 g.

Anal. : Re, 39.8; Cl, 23.2; N, 5.9; C, 25.9; H, 2.1; oxidation state of rhenium, +5.04.
Calcd. for $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$: Re, 39.9; Cl, 22.8; N, 6.0; C, 25.7; H, 2.2; oxidation state of rhenium, +5.00.

Properties of the complexes: All these three complexes are insoluble in water and in ethanol. The violet form of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ is soluble in acetone, while the green form of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ and the green complex $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$ are very sparingly soluble in acetone.

The violet form of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ on standing gradually turns dirty green and finally pure green without any change in weight. All these complexes decompose with the liberation of pyridine on warming with alkali solution. A saturated aqueous solution ($2.01 \times 10^{-4} M$) of $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$ is very weakly conducting ($\mu_v = 18.9 \text{ ohm}^{-1}$ at 30°). On triturating an aqueous suspension of $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$ with excess of silver nitrate, no silver chloride is formed.

DISCUSSION

For the protonation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ to $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4]^{+2}$ the value of $\log k$ was found to be 1.7 at 27° (Table I). This shows that for the system $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+ \rightarrow [\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4]^{+2}$ the equilibrium lies largely to the left unless the concentration of acid added is very large. Since the \bar{n} value did not exceed 0.4, the ion $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{py}_4]^{+3}$ is not present to any appreciable extent in the range of acid concentration studied and accordingly the second acid association constant could not be determined.

Recently Beard, Casey and Murmann⁶ have studied the acid association of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$. They have spectrophotometrically determined that at an approximate pH of -0.57 , half of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ is converted to the monoprotonated species. However, as stated by the workers, the results are inaccurate because of simultaneous decomposition of the complex at the high acidity used, and the high ionic strength. They obtained no indication of the addition of second proton to the pyridine complex even in very strong HCl medium. The general agreement of the findings in the present work and by Beard *et al.* is thus apparent, although the studies have been made by two distinct methods.

The relationship between the green and the violet forms of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ is particularly interesting. These might be conceived to be cis-trans isomers, or one form (the green one) may be a polymer. Studies on magnetic property and IR spectra of the complexes throw some light into this aspect. Table 2 indicates that after making diamagnetic corrections for the ligands, a small paramagnetism ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.69 \text{ B.M.}$) seems to be associated for $\text{Re}(\text{V})$ in the green form, while the violet complex was still diamagnetic ($\chi_M' = -45 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units). Asmussen and Ballhausen⁷ and Griffith and Orgel⁸ have shown from theoretical considerations that the magnetic susceptibilities of geometrical isomers are expected to be practically identical. The difference in the magnetic susceptibilities of the two forms therefore suggests that they are not geometrical isomers. Gill *et al.*⁴ have studied the IR spectra of pyridine and a large number of transition metal complexes containing coordinated pyridine. Their studies indicated that the strong peaks of pyridine at 1578 and at 601 cm^{-1} were shifted to $1600\text{--}1615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $622\text{--}641 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively on complex formation. The violet and the green forms of $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ also gave characteristic peaks in this region. Except around 3300 , 980 and 750 cm^{-1} the other peaks of the two complexes were generally similar to those observed by Gill *et al.* The band at 747 cm^{-1} for pyridine which was found to shift from $741\text{--}769 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in coordinated pyridine complexes, was split in these two complexes to give two strong bands at 755 and 765 cm^{-1} . The peaks observed at 978 and at 980 cm^{-1} for the violet and the green forms respectively were the characteristic $\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretching

6. J. H. Beard, J. Casey and R. K. Murmann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 797.

7. R. W. Asmussen and C. J. Ballhausen, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 479.

8. J. S. Griffith and L. E. Orgel, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 601.

frequencies. It is interesting to note that while the violet form gave the characteristic OH frequency at 3330 cm^{-1} , this was absent in the green complex. The formulation of the green form based on chemical analysis is thus incompatible with the IR data. The complex might be a polymerised one. The simplest polymer of a compound having the composition $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ might have a formulation of $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$. A compound of this formulation has actually been isolated⁵, the IR spectrum of which is however, different from that of the green complex of composition $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$. The position regarding the actual formulation of the green compound thus remains unsettled without further experimental evidences.

Recently Beard *et al.*⁶ have reported the isolation of a dark green substance of the composition $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2$ by the action of 1 *M* HCl on $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$. This gave IR bands in the region $700\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 640, 662, 6787, 757, 767 and 980 cm^{-1} and its corrected magnetic moment value was 0.73 B.M. at 298° K . Banerjee *et al.*⁹ have also reported a similar product of the same composition, the IR spectra of which gave no OH band. It appears that our green product is identical with that obtained by Beard *et al.* and Banerjee *et al.*, although it could not be ascertained whether their product contained any violet component.

The composition and the nonelectrolytic structure of the green compound $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$ is based on elemental analysis, determination of the oxidation state of rhenium, nonconductance of a very dilute aqueous solution of the substance, inability of the compound to form any silver chloride on trituration with silver nitrate solution, presence of characteristic bands at 970 (vs) and 940 (m) cm^{-1} ($\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretch) and absence of OH band in the IR spectra of the substance.

Several communications reporting the isolation of green products by the action of HCl on $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ have been published by different groups of workers. Sur and Sen¹⁰ have obtained a green product by boiling $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{I}$ with concentrated HCl and this they formulated as $\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_5\text{py}_2$. The authors have not reported the percentage composition of the elements or adduced any evidence in favour of the $+7$ oxidation state of rhenium which is evident from their formulation. Beard *et al.*⁶ have obtained a pale green precipitate by boiling a solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ in concentrated HCl and this they formulated as $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, without giving any evidence in favour of the suggested cationic structure. The difference in the empirical composition of the product of Beard *et al.* and ours is one molecule of H_2O and it is interesting to note that Beard *et al.*'s analysis fits as well or even probably better with the formulation $\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_3$. It appears that Beard *et al.* have inclined greatly on the oxygen content of the substance which analysis we could not do.

Recently Grove and Wilkinson¹¹ have reported the preparation of a green product by boiling $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with 5 *N* or 10 *N* HCl and the product has been formulated as $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4][\text{ReOCl}_5]$. Their formulation is based on the analytical data of C, H, N and O and the presence of cationic and anionic $\text{Re} = \text{O}$ stretches in the IR spectra at 968 and 940 cm^{-1} respectively. Deuteration failed to shift the above bands, and thus according to

9. S. B. Banerjee and B. Sur. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28** 2423.

10. B. Sur and D. Sen, *Science and Culture* (Calcutta), 1960, **26**, 85.

11. D. E. Grove and G. Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 1224.

the authors Beard *et al.*'s formulation of $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{py}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ is not tenable. Lebedinskii and Ivanov-Emin's¹ previous formulation of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]_2[\text{ReOCl}_5]$ for the green product is also not favoured by these authors on the ground that the presence of the cation $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ in the product which was obtained from a strongly acidic solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ is highly unlikely. In the absence of any percentage composition of Re and Cl, the ratio of which appears to be 1 : 2.5 from Grove *et al.*'s formulation, we could not confirm the identity of their product with ours in which the Re : Cl ratio has been clearly shown to be 1 : 3.

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